

Uniqueness of k^{th} Derivative of an Entire Function that Shares Pair of Small Functions with its Shift

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Abstract

The main objective of this article is to investigate the uniqueness of higher-order derivatives of an entire function sharing two distinct pairs of small functions with its function $f(z)$. Meanwhile, we obtain the main result, from which we deduce several corollaries, and all those corollaries greatly expand the results, which improve results due to Qi [14], Qi, and Yang [15], X. Huang, and M. Fang [13].

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1. INTRODUCTION

Let \mathbb{C} denote the complex plane, and the term meromorphic will always mean meromorphic in the complex plane. We use the standard notations in the Nevanlinna theory (see, e.g., [8], [11], [17], [18]). In particular $S(r, f)$ means any quantity of growth $o(T(r, f))$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$ outside of a possible exceptional set with a finite logarithmic measure. Let f and g be two non-constant meromorphic functions, and α and β be small functions with respect to f and g . If the zeros of $f - \alpha$ and $g - \beta$ concur in locations and multiplicities, then we say that f and g share the pair of small functions (α, β) CM (counting multiplicities), and if we do not consider the multiplicities, then f and g are said to share the pair of small functions (α, β) IM (ignoring multiplicities).

Moreover, we introduce the following notations: $S_{(p,q)}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) = \{z | z \text{ is a common zero of } f(z+c) - \alpha_1 \text{ and } f^{(k)}(z) - \alpha_2 \text{ with multiplicities } p \text{ and } q, \text{ respectively}\}$. Now the notations $N_{(p,q)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\alpha_1}\right)$ and $\bar{N}_{(p,q)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\alpha_1}\right)$ denote the counting function and the reduced counting function of f with respect to the set $S_{(p,q)}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$, respectively. The

notations $N_{(p,q)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z)-\alpha_2}\right)$ and $\bar{N}_{(p,q)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z)-\alpha_2}\right)$ can be similarly defined.

The following definitions are used in this paper:

Definition 1.1. *The order of a meromorphic function f is denoted by $\rho(f)$ and defined by*

$$\rho(f) = \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log^+ T(r, f)}{\log r}.$$

Definition 1.2. *The hyper-order of a meromorphic function f is denoted by $\rho_2(f)$ and defined by*

$$\rho_2(f) = \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log^+ \log^+ T(r, f)}{\log r}.$$

Value distribution theory is being used by many mathematicians to investigate the uniqueness of functions.

In 2011, G. X. Qi[14] proved the following uniqueness result:

Theorem 1.1. *Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant entire function of finite order. Let c be a non-zero finite complex value, and let a, b be two distinct complex values. If $f(z)$ and $f(z+c)$ share a, b IM, then $f(z) \equiv f(z+c)$.*

Here, we summarise some recent findings about the uniqueness of $f(z)$ and $f'(z)$ with $f(z+c)$ when they share values.

X. Qi and L. Yang[15] considered theorem 1.1 for the derivative of $f(z)$ and proved the following results:

Theorem 1.2. *Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant entire function of finite order, and let a, c be two non-zero finite complex values. If $f'(z)$ and $f(z+c)$ share 0 CM and a IM, then $f'(z) \equiv f(z+c)$.*

Theorem 1.3. *Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental entire function of finite order. Let c be a non-zero finite complex value, and let a, b be two distinct finite values. If $f'(z)$ and $f(z+c)$ share a, b IM, and $\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f' - a}\right) = S(r, f)$. Then $f'(z) \equiv f(z+c)$.*

X. Huang and M. Fang[13] improved the above theorems and proved the following result:

Theorem 1.4. *Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental entire function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, let c be a non-zero finite complex value, and a, b be two distinct finite values. If $f'(z)$ and $f(z+c)$ share a, b IM, then $f'(z) \equiv f(z+c)$.*

X. Huang, B. Deng, and M. Fang[12] investigated the uniqueness of $f(z)$ and $f^{(k)}(z)$ when they share the pair values and as a result, they proved the following theorem.

Theorem 1.5. *Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant entire function. Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ be four small functions of $f(z)$ such that $\alpha_1 \not\equiv \beta_1$ and $\alpha_2 \not\equiv \beta_2$, and none of them identically equal to ∞ . If $f(z)$ and $f^{(k)}(z)$ share (α_1, α_2) , CM and (β_1, β_2) IM, then $(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f^{(k)}(z) \equiv \alpha_2\beta_1 - \alpha_1\beta_2$.*

Here, we note that in the case of sharing values IM, W. W. Adams and E. G. Straus[1] proved the following theorem.

Theorem 1.6. *Let f and g be non-constant polynomials and a, b be distinct finite complex numbers. If f and g share a and b IM, then $f \equiv g$.*

By the above theorem, we will restrict our attention to only transcendental entire functions when they share two values IM to investigate their uniqueness. This paper investigates what can be claimed when $f(z)$ is replaced by $f(z+c)$, and one CM and one IM shared a pair of small functions are replaced by both IM shared pairs of small functions in theorem 1.5. In fact, we demonstrate the following theorem, as the main result of this paper that greatly expands the above mentioned theorems:

Theorem 1.7. *Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental entire function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, k be a non-negative integer, c be a non-zero finite complex value, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ be four small functions of $f(z)$ such that $\alpha_1 \not\equiv \beta_1$ and $\alpha_2 \not\equiv \beta_2$, and each of them not equal to ∞ . If $f(z+c)$ and $f^{(k)}(z)$ share (α_1, α_2) and (β_1, β_2) IM, and $T(r, f(z+c)) \leq T(r, f^{(k)}) + S(r, f)$, then $(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f^{(k)}(z) \equiv \alpha_2\beta_1 - \alpha_1\beta_2$.*

The following examples justify the Theorem 1.7.

Example 1.1. *Let $f(z) = e^z$ and $c = \pi i$. Then $f(z+c) = e^{z+\pi i}$, $\alpha_1 = 2, \alpha_2 = -2, \beta_1 = 1, \beta_2 = -1$. Then, we see that $f(z+c)$ and $f^{(k)}(z)$ share both (α_1, α_2) and (β_1, β_2) . Clearly, we find that $(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f^{(k)}(z) + \alpha_1\beta_2 - \alpha_2\beta_1 \equiv 0$.*

Example 1.2. *Let $f(z) = e^{5z}$, and $c = \pi i$. Then $f(z+c) = e^{5(z+\pi i)}$, $\alpha_1 = -1, \alpha_2 = 25, \beta_1 = -2, \beta_2 = 50$. Then, we see that $f(z+c)$ and*

$f''(z)$ share both (α_1, α_2) and (β_1, β_2) . Clearly, we find that $(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f''(z) + \alpha_1\beta_2 - \alpha_2\beta_1 \equiv 0$.

The following are the inherent and natural results of our Theorem 1.7.

Corollary 1.1. *Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental entire function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, let c be a non-zero finite complex value, and β_1, β_2 be distinct small functions, and each of them is not equal to ∞ . If $f(z+c)$ and $f^{(k)}(z)$ share (β_1, β_2) IM and $E(0, f(z+c)) \subseteq E(0, f^{(k)})$, then $\beta_1 f^{(k)} = \beta_2 f(z+c)$.*

Corollary 1.2. *Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental entire function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, let c be a non-zero finite complex value, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ be four small functions, such that $\alpha_1 \not\equiv \beta_1$ and $\alpha_2 \not\equiv \beta_2$, and none of them is exactly equal to ∞ . If $f(z+c)$ and $f^{(k)}(z)$ share (α_1, α_2) and (β_1, β_2) IM, and $\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)} - \alpha_2}\right) = S(r, f)$. Then $(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f^{(k)}(z) \equiv \alpha_2\beta_1 - \alpha_1\beta_2$.*

It is worth pointing out that our theorem 1.7 for the special case of $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ as constants leads to the following corollaries.

Corollary 1.3. *Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental entire function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, let c be a non-zero finite complex value, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ be four finite constants such that $\alpha_1 \neq \beta_1$ and $\alpha_2 \neq \beta_2$. If $f(z+c)$ and $f'(z)$ share (α_1, α_2) and (β_1, β_2) IM, then $(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f'(z) \equiv \alpha_2\beta_1 - \alpha_1\beta_2$.*

Corollary 1.4. *Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental entire function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, let c be a non-zero finite complex value, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ be four small functions such that $\alpha_1 \not\equiv \beta_1$ and $\alpha_2 \not\equiv \beta_2$. If $f(z+c)$ and $f(z)$ share (α_1, α_2) and (β_1, β_2) IM, then $(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f(z+c) \equiv \alpha_2\beta_1 - \alpha_1\beta_2$.*

2. Some preliminary results

In this section, we present the auxiliary results needed to prove the theorem 1.7

Lemma 2.1. [10]

Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant meromorphic function of hyper-order $\rho_2(f) < 1$ and $c \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$. Then, for any $c \in \mathbb{C}$, we have

$$m\left(r, \frac{f(z+c)}{f(z)}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{f(z)}{f(z+c)}\right) = S(r, f).$$

Lemma 2.2. [17]

Suppose that $f(z)$ is a meromorphic function in the complex plane, and a_1, a_2 , and a_3 are three distinct small functions of $f(z)$. Then

$$T(r, f) \leq \sum_{j=1}^3 \overline{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{f - a_j} \right) + S(r, f).$$

Lemma 2.3. [17]

Let $f_1(z)$ and $f_2(z)$ be non-constant meromorphic functions, in $|z| < \infty$, then

$$N(r, f_1 f_2) - N \left(r, \frac{1}{f_1 f_2} \right) = N(r, f_1) + N(r, f_2) - N \left(r, \frac{1}{f_1} \right) - N \left(r, \frac{1}{f_2} \right),$$

where $0 < r < \infty$.

Lemma 2.4. [10]

Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant meromorphic function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, and let c be a non-zero complex number. Then

$$T(r, f(z)) = T(r, f(z + c)) + S(r, f).$$

Lemma 2.5. [17]

Let $f(z)$ be an entire function and k be a positive integer. Then

$$m \left(r, \frac{f^{(k)}(z)}{f(z)} \right) = S(r, f).$$

The idea for considering the following Lemma 2.6 and Lemma 2.7 is taken from the results of X. Huang, B. Deng, and M.Fang[12].

Lemma 2.6. Let f be a transcendental meromorphic function, let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ be four small functions of $f(z)$ such that $\alpha_1 \not\equiv \beta_1$ and $\alpha_2 \not\equiv \beta_2$, and let

$$L(f(z+c)) = \begin{vmatrix} f(z+c) - \alpha_1 & \alpha_1 - \beta_1 \\ f'(z+c) - \alpha'_1 & \alpha'_1 - \beta'_1 \end{vmatrix}, \quad L(f^{(k)}(z)) = \begin{vmatrix} f^{(k)}(z) - \alpha_2 & \alpha_2 - \beta_2 \\ f^{(k+1)}(z) - \alpha'_2 & \alpha'_2 - \beta'_2 \end{vmatrix}.$$

If $f(z+c)$ and $f^{(k)}(z)$ share (α_1, α_2) and (β_1, β_2) IM, then

$$L(f^{(k)}(z)) \not\equiv 0, L(f(z+c)) \not\equiv 0.$$

Proof. Suppose that $L(f(z+c)) \equiv 0$. Then we get $\frac{f'(z+c) - \alpha'_1}{f(z+c) - \alpha_1} =$

$\frac{\alpha'_1 - \beta'_1}{\alpha_1 - \beta_1}$. It follows that $f(z+c) - \alpha_1 = t(\alpha_1 - \beta_1)$, where t is a non-zero constant. So $T(r, f(z+c)) = T(r, t(\alpha_1 - \beta_1) + \alpha_1) = S(r, f)$, a contradiction. Hence, $L(f(z+c)) \not\equiv 0$.

Since α_2 and β_2 are small functions of $f^{(k)}(z)$, and using the same argument as proving $L(f(z+c)) \not\equiv 0$, it is easy to obtain $L(f^{(k)}(z)) \not\equiv 0$. \square

Lemma 2.7. *Let f be a transcendental meromorphic function, let $k_j (j = 1, 2, \dots, q)$ be positive integers, and let α_1, β_1 be two distinct small functions of $f(z)$ and let $\gamma_j = \alpha_1 - k_j(\alpha_1 - \beta_1) (j = 1, 2, \dots, q)$. Then*

$$(i) m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))}{f(z+c) - \alpha_1} \right) = S(r, f), \quad (ii) m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right) = S(r, f),$$

$$(iii) m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))}{(f(z+c) - \gamma_j)} \right) = S(r, f), \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, q.$$

$$(iv) m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))}{(f(z+c) - \gamma_1)(f(z+c) - \gamma_2) \cdots (f(z+c) - \gamma_q)} \right) = S(r, f),$$

$$(v) m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))f(z+c)}{(f(z+c) - \gamma_1)(f(z+c) - \gamma_2) \cdots (f(z+c) - \gamma_m)} \right) = S(r, f),$$

where $L(f(z+c))$ as defined in Lemma 2.6, and $2 \leq m \leq q$.

Proof. : Using Lemma 2.5, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (i) m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))}{f(z+c) - \alpha_1} \right) &\leq m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha'_1 - \beta'_1)(f(z+c) - \alpha_1)}{f(z+c) - \alpha_1} \right) \\ &\quad + m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha_1 - \beta_1)(f'(z+c) - \alpha'_1)}{f(z+c) - \alpha_1} \right) + S(r, f) = S(r, f), \\ (ii) m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right) &= m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha'_1 - \beta'_1)(f(z+c) - \alpha_1) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)(f'(z+c) - \alpha'_1)}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right) \\ &= m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha'_1 - \beta'_1)f(z+c) - \alpha_1(\alpha'_1 - \beta'_1) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f'(z+c) + \alpha'_1(\alpha_1 - \beta_1) + \beta'_1\beta_1 - \beta'_1\beta_1}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right) \\ &= m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha'_1 - \beta'_1)(f(z+c) - \beta_1) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)(f'(z+c) - \beta'_1)}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right) \\ &\leq m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha'_1 - \beta'_1)(f(z+c) - \beta_1)}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right) + m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha_1 - \beta_1)(f'(z+c) - \beta'_1)}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right) + S(r, f) \\ &= S(r, f), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (iii) \ m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))}{(f(z+c) - \gamma_j)} \right) \\
& = \ m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha'_1 - \beta'_1)(f(z+c) - \alpha_1) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)(f'(z+c) - \alpha'_1)}{f(z+c) - \gamma_j} \right) \\
& \leq \ m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha'_1 - \beta'_1) [f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - k_j(\alpha_1 - \beta_1))]}{f(z+c) - \gamma_j} \right) \\
& + \ m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha_1 - \beta_1) [f'(z+c) - (\alpha'_1 - k_j(\alpha'_1 - \beta'_1))]}{f(z+c) - \gamma_j} \right) + S(r, f). \\
& \leq \ m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha'_1 - \beta'_1) [f(z+c) - \gamma_j]}{f(z+c) - \gamma_j} \right) \\
& + \ m \left(r, \frac{(\alpha_1 - \beta_1) [f'(z+c) - \gamma'_j]}{f(z+c) - \gamma_j} \right) + S(r, f) = S(r, f).
\end{aligned}$$

$$(iv) \ \frac{L(f(z+c))}{(f(z+c) - \gamma_1)(f(z+c) - \gamma_2) \cdots (f(z+c) - \gamma_q)} = \sum_{i=1}^q \frac{A_i L(f(z+c))}{f(z+c) - \gamma_i},$$

where $A_i = \frac{1}{\prod_{j \neq i} (\gamma_i - \gamma_j)}$ are small functions of $f(z)$. By Lemma 2.1 and above, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))}{(f(z+c) - \gamma_1)(f(z+c) - \gamma_2) \cdots (f(z+c) - \gamma_q)} \right) \\
& = m \left(r, \sum_{i=1}^q \frac{A_i L(f(z+c))}{f(z+c) - \gamma_i} \right) \leq \sum_{i=1}^q m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))}{f(z+c) - \gamma_i} \right) + S(r, f) = S(r, f).
\end{aligned}$$

$$(v) \ \frac{L(f(z+c))f(z+c)}{(f(z+c) - \gamma_1)(f(z+c) - \gamma_2) \cdots (f(z+c) - \gamma_m)} = \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{A_i L(f(z+c))}{f(z+c) - \gamma_i},$$

where $A_i = \frac{\gamma_j}{\prod_{j \neq i} (\gamma_i - \gamma_j)}$ are small functions of $f(z)$. By Lemma 2.1 and above, we have

$$m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))f(z+c)}{(f(z+c) - \gamma_1)(f(z+c) - \gamma_2) \cdots (f(z+c) - \gamma_m)} \right)$$

$$= m \left(r, \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{A_i L(f(z+c))}{f(z+c) - \gamma_i} \right) \leq \sum_{i=1}^m m \left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))}{f(z+c) - \gamma_i} \right) + S(r, f) = S(r, f).$$

□

Using the same arguments as in the proof of Lemma 2.7, we obtain the following Lemma

Lemma 2.8. *Let f be a transcendental meromorphic function, let $k_j (j = 1, 2, \dots, q)$ be positive integers, and let α_1, β_1 be two distinct small functions of f and let $\gamma_j = \alpha_2 - k_j(\alpha_2 - \beta_2) (j = 1, 2, \dots, q)$. Then*

$$(i) m \left(r, \frac{L(f^{(k)}(z))}{f^{(k)}(z) - \alpha_2} \right) = S(r, f), \quad (ii) m \left(r, \frac{L(f^{(k)}(z))}{f^{(k)}(z) - \beta_2} \right) = S(r, f),$$

$$(iii) m \left(r, \frac{L(f^{(k)}(z))}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_j} \right) = S(r, f), \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, q$$

$$(iv) m \left(r, \frac{L(f^{(k)}(z))}{(f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_1)(f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2) \cdots (f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_q)} \right) = S(r, f),$$

and

$$(v) m \left(r, \frac{L(f^{(k)}(z))f^{(k)}(z)}{(f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_1)(f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2) \cdots (f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_m)} \right) = S(r, f),$$

where $L(f^{(k)}(z))$ is defined as in Lemma 2.6, and $2 \leq m \leq q$.

3. Proof of Theorem 1.7

Proof. Assume that $f(z) \neq L^{(k)}(f)$. Since $f(z)$ and $L^{(k)}(f)$ share a and b IM, and f is a transcendental entire function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, then by the Nevanlinna Second Fundamental Theorem, Lemma 2.1, Lemma 2.2, and Lemma 2.4, we get,

$$\begin{aligned}
T(r, f(z)) &\leq \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \alpha_1}\right) + \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \beta_1}\right) \\
&+ \overline{N}(r, f(z)) + S(r, f) \\
&= \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L^{(k)}(f) - \alpha_1}\right) + \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L^{(k)}(f) - \beta_1}\right) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq N\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - L^{(k)}(f)}\right) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq T(r, f(z+c) - L^{(k)}(f)) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq m(r, f(z) - L^{(k)}(f)) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq m(r, f(z+c)) + m\left(r, \frac{f(z) - L^{(k)}(f)}{f(z)}\right) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq T(r, f(z)) + S(r, f).
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have

$$T(r, f(z)) = \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \alpha_1}\right) + \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \beta_1}\right) + S(r, f). \quad (3.1)$$

Set

$$\Phi(z) = \frac{K(f(z))(f(z) - L^{(k)}(f))}{(f(z) - \alpha_1)(f(z) - \beta_1)} \quad (3.2)$$

and

$$\Psi(z) = \frac{L(f^{(k)})((\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f^{(k)}(z) + \alpha_1\beta_2 - \alpha_2\beta_1)}{(f^{(k)}(z) - \alpha_2)(f^{(k)}(z) - \beta_2)} \quad (3.3)$$

By the hypothesis, Φ is an entire function and using Lemma 2.1, 2.5-2.7, we have

$$\begin{aligned} T(r, \Phi(z)) &= m(r, \Phi(z)) \\ &= m\left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))((\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f^{(k)}(z) + \alpha_1\beta_2 - \alpha_2\beta_1)}{(f(z+c) - \alpha_1)(f(z+c) - \beta_1)}\right) \\ &\leq m\left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))f(z+c)}{(f(z+c) - \alpha_1)(f(z+c) - \beta_1)}\right) \\ &\quad + m\left(r, \frac{(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f^{(k)}(z)}{f(z+c)}\right) \\ &\quad + m\left(\frac{L(f(z+c))(\alpha_1\beta_2 - \beta_1\alpha_2)}{(f(z+c) - \alpha_1)(f(z+c) - \beta_1)}\right) + S(r, f) = S(r, f) \end{aligned}$$

That is

$$T(r, \Phi) = S(r, f). \quad (3.4)$$

Let $\gamma_1 = \alpha_1 - k(\alpha_1 - \beta_1)$ and $\gamma_2 = \alpha_2 - k(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)$. It follows from Nevanlinna's second fundamental theorem and (3.1) that

$$\begin{aligned} 2T(r, f(z+c)) &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \alpha_1}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \beta_1}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) \\ &\quad + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, f(z+c)) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq 2T(r, f(z+c)) - m\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

Which implies

$$m\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) = S(r, f). \quad (3.5)$$

We have

$$T(r, f^{(k)}) = m(r, f^{(k)}) \leq m\left(r, \frac{f^{(k)}}{f}\right) + m(r, f) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq m(r, f) + S(r, f) \leq T(r, f) + S(r, f)$$

Using this with Lemma 2.4, we get

$$T(r, f^{(k)}(z)) \leq T(r, f(z+c)) + S(r, f) \quad (3.6)$$

Using (3.6) with the hypothesis, we get

$$T(r, f(z+c)) = T(r, f^{(k)}(z)) + S(r, f) \quad (3.7)$$

By the Second Nevanlinna Fundamental theorem, (3.1) and (3.7), we have

$$\begin{aligned} 2T(r, f(z+c)) &\leq 2T(r, f^{(k)}(z)) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \alpha_2}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \beta_2}\right) \\ &\quad + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \alpha_1}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \beta_1}\right) \\ &\quad + T\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}\right) - m\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, f(z+c)) + T(r, f^{(k)}(z)) - m\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq 2T(r, f(z+c)) - m\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}\right) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we get

$$m\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}\right) = S(r, f). \quad (3.8)$$

Since $f(z)$ is an entire function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$ and using the first fundamental theorem, Lemma 2.1, 2.3, (3.5), (3.7)-(3.8), we get

$$\begin{aligned} m\left(r, \frac{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}\right) &= T\left(r, \frac{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) - N\left(r, \frac{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq m\left(r, \frac{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_1^{(k)}(z-c)}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{\gamma_1^{(k)}(z-c) - \gamma_2}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) \\ &\quad + N\left(r, \frac{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) - N\left(r, \frac{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}\right) + S(r, f) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq m\left(r, \frac{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_{1-c}^{(k)}}{f^{(k)}(z+c) - \gamma_1^{(k)}(z)}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{f^{(k)}(z+c) - \gamma_1^{(k)}}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{\gamma_{1-c}^{(k)} - \gamma_2}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) \\
&+ N\left(r, \frac{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) - N\left(r, \frac{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}\right) + O(1) \\
&\leq N\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \gamma_1}\right) - N\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2}\right) + S(r, f) \\
&= T(r, f(z+c)) - T(r, f^{(k)}(z)) + S(r, f) \\
&= S(r, f).
\end{aligned} \tag{3.9}$$

By (3.3), we have

$$\Psi(z) = \left[\frac{\alpha_2 - \gamma_2}{\alpha_2 - \beta_2} \frac{L(f^{(k)}(z))}{f^{(k)}(z) - \alpha_2} - \frac{\beta_2 - \gamma_2}{\alpha_2 - \beta_2} \frac{L(f^{(k)}(z))}{f^{(k)}(z) - \beta_2} \right] \left[\frac{(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)(f(z+c) - \gamma_1)}{f^{(k)}(z) - \gamma_2} - \alpha_1 + \beta_1 \right] \tag{3.10}$$

Then, by using Lemma 2.7 and (3.9) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
T(r, \Psi(z)) &= m(r, \Psi(z)) \\
&= S(r, f)
\end{aligned}$$

Let $z_1 \in S_{(p,q)}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \cup S_{(p,q)}(\beta_1, \beta_2)$, where p and q are two positive integers, i.e., z_1 be a common zero of $f(z+c) - \alpha_1$ (resp. $f(z+c) - \beta_1$) and $f^{(k)}(z) - \alpha_2$ (resp. $f^{(k)}(z) - \beta_2$) with multiplicities p and q , respectively. (3.2) and (3.3) imply that $q\Phi(z_1) - p\Psi(z_1) = 0$. Next, we consider the following two cases.

Case 1: $q\Phi(z) - p\Psi(z) \equiv 0$ for some positive integers p and q . It follows that $q\Phi(z) = p\Psi(z)$. Then we have

$$q \left(\frac{L(f(z+c))}{(f(z+c) - \alpha_1)(f(z+c) - \beta_1)} \right) \equiv p \left(\frac{L(f^{(k)}(z))}{(f^{(k)}(z) - \alpha_2)(f^{(k)}(z) - \beta_2)} \right) \tag{3.11}$$

which implies that

$$\left(\frac{f(z+c) - \alpha_1}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right)^q \equiv A \left(\frac{f^{(k)}(z) - \alpha_2}{f^{(k)}(z) - \beta_2} \right)^p \tag{3.12}$$

where A is a non-zero constant. Hence $p = q$; otherwise, we would have a contradiction to (3.7). It follows from (3.12) that

$$B \left(\frac{f(z+c) - \alpha_1}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right) \equiv \left(\frac{f^{(k)}(z) - \alpha_2}{f^{(k)}(z) - \beta_2} \right) \quad (3.13)$$

where $B \neq 1$ is a non-zero constant. Thus, we have

$$\frac{\beta_2 - \alpha_2}{f^{(k)}(z) - \beta_2} = \frac{(B-1)f(z+c) + (\beta_1 - \alpha_1 B)}{f(z+c) - \beta_1}.$$

Since $f(z)$ is an entire function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, it follows that

$$f(z+c) \neq \frac{\beta_1 - \alpha_1 B}{1-B}.$$

Obviously, $(\beta_1 - \alpha_1 B)/(1-B) \neq \alpha_1, \beta_1$. Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 2T(r, f(z+c)) &\leq \bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \alpha_1} \right) + \bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right) \\ &+ \bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \frac{\beta_1 - \alpha_1 B}{1-B}} \right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \alpha_1} \right) + \bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right) + S(r, f) \end{aligned}$$

which contradicts (3.1).

Case 2: $q\Phi(z) \not\equiv p\Psi(z)$ for any positive integers p and q . Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{N}_{(p,q)} \left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \alpha_1} \right) + \bar{N}_{(p,q)} \left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \beta_1} \right) &\leq \bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{q\Phi(z) - p\Psi(z)} \right) \\ &\leq T(r, q\Phi(z) - p\Psi(z)) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, \Phi(z)) + T(r, \Psi(z)) + S(r, f) \\ &= S(r, f), \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

for all positive integers p and q . Thus by (3.7) and (3.14), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
T(r, f(z+c)) &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\alpha_1}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\beta_1}\right) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq \bar{N}_1\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\alpha_1}\right) + \bar{N}_2\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\alpha_1}\right) \\
&\quad + \bar{N}_3\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\alpha_1}\right) + \bar{N}_4\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\alpha_1}\right) \\
&\quad + \bar{N}_{(5)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\alpha_1}\right) + \bar{N}_1\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\beta_1}\right) \\
&\quad + \bar{N}_2\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\beta_1}\right) + \bar{N}_3\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\beta_1}\right) \\
&\quad + \bar{N}_4\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\beta_1}\right) + \bar{N}_{(5)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\beta_1}\right) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq \sum_{q=1}^4 \sum_{p=1}^4 \bar{N}_{(p,q)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\alpha_1}\right) + \bar{N}_{(5)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z)-\alpha_1}\right) \\
&\quad + \bar{N}_{(5)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\alpha_1}\right) + \sum_{q=1}^4 \sum_{p=1}^4 \bar{N}_{(p,q)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\beta_1}\right) \\
&\quad + \bar{N}_{(5)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z)-\beta_1}\right) + \bar{N}_{(5)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\beta_1}\right) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq \frac{1}{5} \left[N\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\alpha_1}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)-\beta_1}\right) \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{5} \left[N\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z)-\alpha_2}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z)-\beta_2}\right) \right] + S(r, f) \\
&\leq \frac{2}{5} T(r, f(z+c)) + \frac{2}{5} T(r, f^{(k)}(z)) + S(r, f) \\
&= \frac{4}{5} T(r, f(z+c)) + S(r, f) \tag{3.15}
\end{aligned}$$

which gives a contradiction to the hypothesis that $f(z)$ is transcendental function. \square

3.1. Proof of Corollary 1.1.

Proof. Since $E(0, f(z+c)) \subseteq E(0, f^{(k)})$, we get

$$N\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)}\right) \leq N\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}}\right). \quad (3.16)$$

Also, using Lemma 2.1 and Lemma 2.5, we attain

$$\begin{aligned} m\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c)}\right) &\leq m\left(r, \frac{f^{(k)}}{f(z+c)}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq m\left(r, \frac{f^{(k)}(z)}{f(z)}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{f(z)}{f(z+c)}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}}\right) + S(r, f). \\ &\leq m\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z)}\right) + S(r, f). \end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

From (3.16) and (3.17), we obtain

$$T(r, f(z+c)) \leq T(r, f^{(k)}) + S(r, f). \quad (3.18)$$

Using theorem 1.7, we get $\beta_1 f^{(k)} = \beta_2 f(z+c)$. \square

3.2. Proof of Corollary 1.2.

Proof. Since $\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)} - \alpha_2}\right) = S(r, f)$, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} T(r, f(z+c)) &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \alpha_1}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z+c) - \beta_1}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \alpha_2}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f^{(k)}(z) - \beta_2}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, f^{(k)}) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

Using theorem 1.7, we get $(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f^{(k)}(z) \equiv \alpha_2\beta_1 - \alpha_1\beta_2$. \square

3.3. Proof of Corollary 1.3.

Proof. Using $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ are constants, and $k = 1$ in the Lemma 2.6, we have $L(f(z+c)) = (\beta_1 - \alpha_1)f'(z+c)$ and $L(f'(z)) = (\beta_2 - \alpha_2)f''(z)$. Set

$$\Phi_1(z) = \frac{L(f(z+c))((\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f'(z) + \alpha_1\beta_2 - \alpha_2\beta_1)}{(f(z+c) - \alpha_1)(f(z+c) - \beta_1)} \quad (3.19)$$

$$\Psi_1(z) = \frac{L(f'(z))((\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f'(z) + \alpha_1\beta_2 - \alpha_2\beta_1)}{(f'(z) - \alpha_2)(f'(z) - \beta_2)} \quad (3.20)$$

Equation (3.19) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_1(z)f^2(z+c) &= L(f(z+c))((\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f') \\ &+ (\alpha_1\beta_2 - \alpha_2\beta_1)L(f(z+c)) + (\alpha_1 + \beta_1)f(z+c)\Phi_1(z) - \alpha_1\beta_1\Phi_1(z). \end{aligned}$$

Using the first fundamental theorem, Lemmas 2.1 and 2.4, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \quad T(r, f(z+c)) &= T(r, f(z+c)^2) = T\left(r, \frac{1}{\Phi_1(z)}\right) \\ &+ T(r, L(f(z+c))((\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f') + (\alpha_1\beta_2 - \alpha_2\beta_1)L(f(z+c)) \\ &+ (\alpha_1 + \beta_1)f(z+c)\Phi_1(z) - \alpha_1\beta_1\Phi_1(z)) \\ &\leq m(r, f(z+c)) \\ &+ m\left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))((\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f'(z)) + (\alpha_1\beta_2 - \alpha_2\beta_1)L(f(z+c))}{f(z+c)}\right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{(\alpha_1 + \beta_1)f(z+c)\Phi_1(z)}{f(z+c)}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq m(r, f(z+c)) + m(r, f'(z)) + m\left(r, \frac{L(f(z+c))((\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f'(z))}{f(z+c)f'(z)}\right) \\ &+ S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, f(z+c)) + T(r, f'(z)) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$T(r, f(z+c)) \leq T(r, f'(z)) + S(r, f)$$

Now, using theorem 1.7, we get $(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f'(z) \equiv \alpha_2\beta_1 - \alpha_1\beta_2$. \square

3.4. Proof of Corollary 1.4.

Proof. Since $T(r, f(z+c)) = T(r, f) + S(r, f)$, using theorem 1.7, we get $(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f(z+c) \equiv \alpha_2\beta_1 - \alpha_1\beta_2$. \square

4. Open Problem

P. Sahoo and S. Halder [16] proved that

“Let $k \geq 1$ be an integer, and let f be a transcendental entire function of finite order, and a_1, a_2, b_1 , and b_2 be four small functions of f , such

that none of them is identically equal to ∞ , $a_j \not\equiv b_j$ and $a_j - b_j$ has at least one zero for $j = 1, 2$. If $f \in S_k(a_1, a_2; b_1, b_2)$, and f and $f^{(k)}$ share (a_1, a_2) and (b_1, b_2) IM, then $(a_2 - b_2)f - (a_1 - b_1)f^{(k)}(z) \equiv a_2b_1 - a_1b_2$."

Here, it is natural to pose the open question that is it possible to prove the following theorem?

"Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental entire function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, k be a non-negative integer, c be a non-zero finite complex value, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ be four small functions of f such that $\alpha_1 \not\equiv \beta_1$ and $\alpha_2 \not\equiv \beta_2$, and each of them not equal to ∞ . If $f(z+c)$ and $f^{(k)}$ share (α_1, α_2) and (β_1, β_2) IM, then $(\alpha_2 - \beta_2)f(z+c) - (\alpha_1 - \beta_1)f^{(k)}(z) \equiv \alpha_2\beta_1 - \alpha_1\beta_2$."

5. CONCLUSIONS

- We have shown the relationship between the shift and derivative of an entire function sharing two pairs of small functions IM.
- If $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = a$, where $a \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$, then from the corollary 1.1, we have the result, "Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental entire function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, let c be a non-zero finite complex value. If $f(z+c)$ and $f^{(k)}(z)$ share a IM, and $E(0, f(z+c)) \subseteq E(0, f^{(k)})$, then $f^{(k)} = f(z+c)$ ".

This result improves theorem 1.2.

- If $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \alpha$ and $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta$, in corollary 1.2, where α, β are distinct finite constants, then corollary 1.2 is an improvement of theorem 1.3
- We emphasise that corollary 1.3 and corollary 1.4 greatly expands theorem 1.4 and theorem 1.1, from the point of view of sharing values.

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